

DIHNET.EU online Community

DIHNET.EU Community is a collaboration platform that offers DIH networks, DIHs and other key stakeholders a way to interact and look for opportunities among DIHs in Europe; such as participation in projects, joint offers to DIHs, discussion on the selection criteria of DIHs, etc.

WHAT CAN BE FOUND IN THE DIHNET.EU COMMUNITY?

- **Articles:** news, interviews and conclusions related to the DIHs ecosystem.
- **Announcements:** important information for the members of the community.
- **Questions:** this section gather all the questions posed in the community by any member.
- **Events:** announce events of interest for DIHs and the opportunity to meet people that is attending.
- **Showcase:** collection of information listing all EU initiatives supporting DIHs.
- **Real-time chats:** conversation spaces to foster 1:1 interaction.

WHAT DOES THE DIHNET.EU COMMUNITY OFFER?

- Access to **training** (webinars) on community building, business models and more.
- **Guidance & Support** to take advantage of the DIHNET.EU community.
- Become one of the **featured initiatives supporting** DIHs and gain visibility.
- Invite other **DIHs to join your network** and offer them your services.

- Become an **active member** of the DIHNET.EU community by sharing articles and information related to your project activities (newsletters, events).
- Get first-hand and fresh **collaboration opportunities to offer to the DIHs** in your network.
- Create a **private space** within the DIHNET.EU platform for your internal communications and ensure your DIHs are represented in the DIHNET.EU community.

- Invite your DIHs to **participate in the working groups** & decide on the future of DIHs.

- **Take part/benefit from DIHNET online & offline events** and offer them to the DIHs within your network. Events such as Q&A, international events, follow-up on the DIHs Working Groups of the EC and many more.

We will be happy to **guide you through the community features** and **get your network to the next level!**

For more information on [DIHNET.EU](https://www.dihnet.eu) online community, contact:

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Join the
DIHNET.EU
 online
 Community